

STUDIES ON THE FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FLAX FIBER/BIO-COMPOSITES

M. Hosur^{1*}, M. Harika², S. Jeelani^{1,2}

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, ² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, AL 36088 USA.

* Corresponding author (hosur@mytut.tuskegee.edu)

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1 Introduction

Biocomposite materials provide a competitive advantage for manufacturers over traditional reinforcing fibers like glass and resins such as polyesters as product reuse or recycling at the end of life becomes the norm [1, 2]. Additionally, technical benefits such as low density, high toughness, acceptable specific strength properties, ease of separation, enhanced energy recovery, carbon dioxide sequestration and biodegradability [3] will all act to drive the growth of markets based on biocomposites [4]. In particular, there is the belief that these technical benefits could have a real impact in the building environment, where improved thermal insulation properties and lower density could result in significant energy savings. Furthermore, the desire to promote use of crops grown for industrial, non-food purposes is driving the uptake of novel composites.

Since commercially available natural fibers are not as strong as graphite or aramid fibers, various modifications of natural fibers and biodegradable resins have been studied to improve their mechanical and surface properties as well as their adhesion to the resins [5-13]. Plant-based fibers mainly consist of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin which are major components of the plant cell wall [2]. Since the strength and stiffness of plant-based fibers mainly depend on their cellulose content, increasing the cellulose content is the key factor to improve the fiber properties. Physical and chemical methods have been used to remove non-cellulose components like pectin, lignin and hemicelluloses resulting in exposing of hydroxyl groups that would interact with polymer as well as reducing the fiber dimensions thereby increasing reacting surface areas. One such technique is alkali treatment of fibers. Hence, in this study, investigations were carried out

to understand sodium hydroxide (NaOH) treatment on the morphology of flax fibers which were then used with two polymers Envirez and polyester to prepare biocomposites. Of the two polymers, Envirez contains blend of natural polymers. Effect of alkali treatment was as studied as a function of NaOH concentration and treatment temperature. For preparing biocomposites, fiber mats were first prepared and used with polymers to manufacture biocomposites using compression molding process. Composites were then tested for their flexure and thermomechanical properties.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Flax fibers used as reinforcement in composites were obtained from Alvin Ulrich Company in Canada. Sodium Hydroxide was obtained from Fisher Scientific. The resins used were as follows: thermoset resins, AOC atryl resin TCA and ENVIREZ 1807 by Ashland.

2.2 Surface Modifications

2.2.1 Concentration treatment

Alkali treatment was done by treating flax fibers with 2.5, 5, and 7% solutions of NaOH concentration for one hour. Fibers were then dried in an oven for 24 hours at 80° C.

2.2.2 Temperature treatment

Fiber surface treatment was carried out at room temperature, 35° C and 45° C with NaOH concentration of 2.5 wt. % for an hour, followed by washing of fibers in distilled water until a neutral pH value was obtained. The fibers were then dried in an oven at 80° C for 24 hours.

2.3 Spectral and thermal analysis

Techniques used to determine morphology of the fibers include X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transfer Infra-Red Spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Optical microscopy. These experiments were done to determine the effect of alkali treatment on fibers. Thermal properties were determined through differential scanning calorimetry studies.

2.4 Fabrication of composites

Fibers mats were prepared by immersing the fibers in water and oven drying them for 24 hours at 80° C. Preparation of bio-composites was done by soaking fiber mats in resin bath and hot pressing the mats using compression molding method for 2 hours at 110° C. Polyester and ENVIREZ 1807 resin systems were used as the matrix to differentiate between the synthetic and biopolymer. Composites were prepared with 3 types of mats (untreated, 2.5wt. %, and temperature treated) and 3 weight percentages (40%, 50%, and 60%) of fibers.

2.5 Characterization

2.5.1 Mechanical testing

The flexural properties of the bio-composites were determined by means of three-point bend test using an INSTRON testing machine as per ASTM standard D3039-08. At least seven samples of each type were tested.

2.5.2 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

To determine the viscoelastic properties, dynamic mechanical analysis test was carried out using double cantilever mode at a frequency of 1 Hz with amplitude of 15 μm. The test temperature was increased from room temperature to 200° C at a rate of 10°/C. Through this test, storage modulus and glass transition temperature (Tg) were determined.

2.5.3 Water absorption rate

Water absorption rate of the composites was determined through ASTM D570-98(2010) test. In this test, composite specimens were soaked in distilled water for a week at room temperature. Samples were weighed each day. Amount of water absorbed by composites was calculated as following:

$$\text{water absorption} = \frac{\text{wet wt} - \text{dry wt}}{\text{dry wt}} \times 100$$

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Surface modifications

3.1.1 XRD analysis

Figure 1 shows XRD spectrum of fibers tested before and after the alkali treatment indicating the change in crystallinity of fibers. Broader XRD peaks with lower intensities suggest lower crystalline material. A lower crystallinity index in case of 5, 7% flax fiber means poor order of cellulose crystals in the fiber. Cellulose crystals were not oriented along the fiber axis. For the fibers that were treated with 2.5% alkali solution, the XRD results show better alignment of cellulose crystals are better oriented along the fiber axis.

Fig.1. XRD of concentration treated fibers.

Fig. 2. XRD of temperature treated fibers.

Fig.2. shows the effect of temperature treatment on flax fibers. The increase in temperature results in the removal of natural polymer from the surface of the fiber bundles. The crystallinity of fibers increases with increase in temperature and decreases at higher temperature. The fibers at 35°C show higher crystallinity compared to 45°C.

3.1.2 FTIR analysis

Figure 3 shows FTIR spectra to illustrate the effect of concentration treatment on fibers whereas the spectra in figure 4 give the results on the effect of temperature treatment on flax fibers. At the range of 700 to 1000 cm^{-1} , the peaks represent the tertiary alkyl groups which are decreasing in treated fibers as alkali treatment dissolves the amorphous cellulose content without modifying the crystalline type of cellulose. Peaks in the range of 1125-1000 cm^{-1} are attributed to typical xylems of plant fiber. Strong peak located at a wavelength of 1040 cm^{-1} shows decrease in intensity as treatment concentration increases. This is attributed to the decrease in absorption of C-O, C-C or C-OH stretching in hemicelluloses. The shoulder at 1254 cm^{-1} belongs to C-O stretching vibration of acetyl groups in lignin component and the peak at 1525 cm^{-1} is due to benzene vibrations of lignin which are seen missing in treated fibers due to effect of mercerization.

Fig.3. Effect of concentration treatment on fibers.

Absorption bands at 3300, 3175 cm^{-1} are typical of the -OH stretching intramolecular hydrogen bonds present in the crystalline cellulose II. From the spectra, the peak for hydroxyl group was highest for as received fibers and this was due to presence of lignin and hemicelluloses absorbing more water. On the other hand, the intensity of -OH groups in

hemicelluloses eventually decreased as alkali concentration increased. It was assumed that when alkali concentration increases the rate of degradation of non-cellulose components would increase.

Fig.4. Effect of temperature treatment on fibers.

Fig.5. SEM micrograph of a) untreated b) 2.5% c) 5%, and d) 7% treated fibers.

3.1.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure 5a shows the micrographs of the untreated flax fiber bundle. The untreated fibers clearly show the binding of individual fibers with each other with the help of natural polymer (lignin). When subjected to alkali treatment, the bonding between individual fibers is seen to decrease (Fig. 5b-d). At 2.5% it appeared that alkali treatment was successful in removing most of the binding from the surface of fiber. As the concentration of alkali increases, fibers were separated. It was believed that due to the deterioration and removal of lignin, the fibers got separated leading to the exposure of reactive sites on

the surface of fiber. However, at higher concentration, it was believed that the cellulosic content was degraded along with hemicellulose and lignin. Fig. 5(d) shows fiber bundles with cracks and breakage resulting from excess alkali treatment.

When the fibers were treated with 2.5 wt.% NaOH solution at 35° C, separation of fiber bundles was seen with some content of hemicelluloses or lignin but when treated with the same concentration of alkali at 45° C, degradation of fiber microstructure was observed with minor cracks visible on the surface as shown in the Fig. 6b.

Fig .6. SEM micrograph of a)2.5%-35°C b)2.5%-45°C

Fig. 7. Water absorption rate of polyester composite

3.2 Characterization of Biocomposites

3.2.1 Water absorption

Figures 7 and 8 show the amount of water absorbed by the biocomposites with polyester and Envirez polymers respectively for different weight content of fibers. In both cases, it is seen that composites with

untreated fibers absorbed most water. As hemicelluloses and lignin are the water absorbing components, higher weight gain is seen in composites with untreated fibers compared to those with treated fibers. When alkali treated these components of the fiber are removed and hence there is a drastic reduction in the amount of water intake. When treated fibers were compared, composites with room temperature treated fibers had higher water absorption relative to those with temperature treated fibers. Envirez composites absorbed less water compared to unsaturated polyester composites. Moisture absorption was the least for 50% fiber weight content in polyester resin system. Composites with untreated fibers and polyester resins with 60 wt. % fibers had the highest absorption rate. This could be attributed to improper wetting of fibers at that high fiber wt. %. Envirez polymer may have better interfacial bonding with flax fibers leading to lower moisture absorption compared to polyester resins. This aspect needs further investigations.

Fig. 8. Water absorption of Envirez composites

3.2.2 Mechanical Properties

Flexural behavior of biocomposites was studied to determine if alkali treatment improved the mechanical properties. Figures 9 and 10 show the flexural strength of polyester and Envirez composites with flax fibers composites prepared with different fiber-matrix ratio. It is observed that the treated composites show higher strength compared to untreated fibers due to better fiber

wetting which enhanced the mechanical interlocking between fiber and matrix. The amount of fiber content also changed the properties of composite. As the fiber content increased, increase in strength was observed for both untreated resin composites but decreases for treated and temperature treated at 60%.

This can be again due to insufficient matrix to completely wet the fibers. Unless, there is good fiber wetting, the composite properties will not improve.

Fig. 9. Flexural strength of polyester composites.

Envirez composites with treated fibers also show increase in strength compared to untreated composites for each fiber-matrix ratio as shown in Fig.10. A decrease in flexural strength is normally indicative of lower fiber-matrix bonding. When compared with composites having polyester resins, composites with Envirez resin have comparable properties. This shows that, it is possible to get comparable properties using polymers that are more environment-friendly.

3.2.3 Viscoelastic properties

Viscoelastic properties of biocomposites were studied to determine the effect of alkali treatment on flax fiber composites through DMA tests. From Fig. 11, it is seen that storage modulus, which give the elastic response of a material under dynamic loading conditions increased with alkali and temperature treatment on fibers. However, storage modulus of these composites decreased for 60 wt. % due to the poor interaction between fiber and the matrix. These results were in agreement with the findings of flexural data given in fig .9.

Fig. 10. Flexural strength of Envirez composites.

Fig. 11. storage modulus of polyester composites.

Fig. 12. Storage modulus of Envirez composites.

Figure 12 shows the effect of alkali treatment on storage modulus of flax fiber composites with Envirez composites. It was observed that Envirez resin has lower viscosity compared to polyester which made easy for the fibers to wet. Comparing the polyester with bio-polyester, Envirez show better wettability of fibers and increase in interfacial bonding compared to polyester composites. Envirez composites also show increase in storage modulus with alkali treatment. Treated fibers give better properties compared to temperature treated. This is due to the removal lignin content from the fibers during temperature treatment and also due to the effect of temperature on the fibers with has increased the reactive sites on the fiber surface.

3.3 Conclusion

Alkali treatment of flax fibers results in the removal of non-cellulose components of the fibers leaving only cellulose with reactive sites to interact with polymers. Further, the treatment has increased surface roughness. Thus, increasing the number of reaction sites which increase the bonding between the polymers and the fiber. This results in increased mechanical, thermomechanical properties of the composites. The morphological analysis on alkali treatment has shown an increase in fiber crystallinity. In case of composites, Envirez composites show better increment in flexural and thermal properties compared to polyester composites as well as reduced water absorption.

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References

- [1] Bartl A., Hackl A., Mihalyi B., Wistuba M. and Marini I., "Recycling of fibre materials," *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.*, 83, 2005, 351-358.
- [2] Netravali, A. N. and Chabba, S., 'Composites Get Greener', *Materials Today*, 2003, pp. 22-29.
- [3] Mohanty A. K., Misra M., and Hinrichsen G., "Biofibres, biodegradable polymers and biocomposites an overview," *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 276, 2000, 1-24.
- [4] Mohanty A. K., Misra M., and Drzal L. T., "Sustainable biocomposites from renewable resources opportunities and challenges in the green materials world," *J Polym. Environ.* 10, 2002, 19-26.
- [5] Goda K, and Cao Y. "Research and development of fully green composites reinforced with natural fibers," *J Solid Mech Mater Engg.* 1(9), 2007, 1073-1084.
- [6] Kim, J. T. and Netravali, A. N., "Mechanical, Thermal, and Interfacial Properties of Green Composites with Ramie Fiber and Soy Resins," *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 58, 2010, 5400-5407. DOI, 10.1021/jf100317y, 2010.
- [7] Kolpak F. J., Weih M., and Blackwell J. "Mercerization of cellulose, 1. Determination of the structure of mercerized cotton," *Polymer* 19(2), 1978, 123-131.
- [8] Geethamma V. G., Thomas M. K, Lakshminarayanan R., and Thomas. S., "Composite of short coir fibres and natural rubber, effect of chemical modification, loading and orientation of fibre," *Polymer*, 39(6-7), 1998, 1483-1491.
- [9] Rosa M. F., Chiou B. S., Medeiros E. S., Wood D. F., Williams T. G., Mattoso L. H. C., Orts W. J., and Imam S. H., "Effect of fiber treatments on tensile and thermal properties of starch/ethylene vinyl alcohol copolymers/coir biocomposites," *Bioresource Techn.* 100(21), 2009, 5196-5202.
- [10] Acha B. A., Reboredo M. M., Marcovich N. E., "Creep and dynamic mechanical behavior of PP-jute composites, Effect of the interfacial adhesion," *Compos Part A*, 38(6), 2007, 1507-1516.
- [11] Pimenta M. T. B., Carvalho A. J. K., Vilaseca F., Girones J., López J. P., Mutjé. P., and Curvelo A. A. S., "Soda-treated sisal/polypropylene composites," *J Polym Environ.*, 2008, 16(1), 35-39.
- [12] Jähn A, Schröder M. W., Fütting M, Schenzel K, and Diepenbrock W. "Characterization of alkali treated flax fibres by means of FT Raman spectroscopy and environmental scanning electron microscopy," *Spectrochim Acta Part A.*, 2002, 58(10), 2271-2279.
- [13] Goda K, Sreekala M. S, Gomes A, Kaji T, and Ohgi J. "Improvement of plant based natural fibers for toughening green composites-Effect of load application during mercerization of ramie fibers," *Compos Part A.*, 2006, 37(12), 2213-2220.